

Atom-economical Ni-catalyzed diborylative cyclization of enynes: preparation of unsymmetrical diboronates

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ABSTRACT: We report a Ni-catalyzed diborylative cyclization of enynes that affords high yields of carbo- and heterocycles containing both alkyl- and alkenylboronates. The reaction is fully atom-economical, shows a broad scope, takes place in smooth conditions and employs a powerful and inexpensive catalytic Ni-based system. Reaction products constitute valuable synthons, which can be orthogonally functionalized. Experimental and computational results support a reaction mechanism involving activation of the enyne by Ni(0) through oxidative cyclometallation of the enyne, prior to diboron reagent activation. An unprecedented dinuclear bis(organometallic) Ni(I) intermediate complex has been isolated.

The development novel efficient synthetic methodology cannot ignore environmental and economic aspects. This is one of the reasons for the renaissance of the Earth-abundant first-row transition metals as catalysts during the last years. Recently, Ni derivatives have demonstrated their utility in a wide variety of synthetically useful reactions.¹ The ability of Ni to access a variety of oxidation states is related to the rich reactivity of Ni derivatives, and the discovery of unprecedented activation pathways.² In addition, cooperative catalysis or a combination of metal-catalyzed and photoredox reactions, constitute novel promising approaches to solve synthetic problems.³ On the other hand, boronates are especially relevant synthons due to their stability, functional group tolerance, low toxicity, versatility and wide applicability.⁴ Preparation of boronates from alkenes, alkynes and other unsaturated compounds by diboration reactions has been performed with a variety of heavy metals.⁵ More recently, Fe,⁶ Co,⁷ Ni⁸, and Cu,⁹ have demonstrated to be useful for these purposes as well. Carboboration,^{10,11} and borylative cyclization reactions,¹² of polyunsaturated compounds constitute powerful methods for the formation of complex boron-containing carbo- and heterocycles by formation of C-C and C-B bonds in cascade reactions. These products are useful synthetic intermediates. Pd-catalyzed borylative cyclizations have proven to be valuable for the preparation of cyclic boronates from di- and polyunsaturated substrates (enyne, enediynes, allenynes, enallenes, etc.) and diboron derivatives,^{13,14} but have some drawbacks, related to the loss of one boryl unit and the difficult catalyst tuning in the necessary ligandless conditions. On the other hand, recently reported Co-¹⁵ Fe-¹⁶ and Ni-catalyzed,¹⁷ hydroborylative cyclizations of enynes with HBpin are far more convenient for their high atom economy, the use of inexpensive catalysts, and the possibility of developing enantioselective transformations.

Herein we wish to report a full atom-economical, versatile, widely applicable synthetic method for the preparation of cyclic compounds containing two different kinds of boronate units, starting from an ample variety of simple enynes by cooperative homometallic catalysis involving Ni complexes. We report the structure of the first unsymmetrical

bis[organonickel(I)] complex, which we propose as the key intermediate for this transformation.

Previous work: monoborylative cyclizations

This work: diborylative cyclization (one C-C and two different C-B bonds)

Scheme 1. Metal-catalyzed mono- and diborylative cyclizations

Our aim was to develop diborylative cyclizations that led to diboronates containing two different boryl units that could be sequentially functionalized. To the best of our knowledge, this process has not been achieved yet. Enynes are especially interesting in this respect, since they may provide diboronates containing to different boryl units. We began our study by searching reaction conditions for the diboration of enyne **1a**. After much experimentation, the desired product **2a** could be obtained using B₂pin₂ (1.05 equiv), Ni(cod)₂ (5 mol%) and 5,5''-dimethylterpyridine (**L1**, 5 mol%) in diisopropylether at 60 °C (see Supporting information for more details on the optimization of the reaction conditions)- Ni(II) salts were ineffective, and led to recovery of the unaltered starting enyne. Although the yield obtained for the model reaction was moderate, the process is very general and proceeds with excellent yields for a wide variety of substrates providing boron-functionalized carbo- and heterocycles (Chart 1).

Thus, enynes containing arylalkynes afforded the corresponding products in moderate to good yields for derivatives with oxygen- (**2a-e**), nitrogen- (**2f-j**, **2r**), or malonate-derived (**2k-n**) within the tethering chains. The reaction tolerates a variety of functional groups with different electronic properties on the aromatic ring (Me, Cl, MeO, CN, and CF₃ in *meta*- and *para*- positions). Simple carbocycles are also accessible in good

yields for substrates containing both aryl and alkyl substituents on the alkyne (**2o–q**, **2s**). Substrates containing methyl-substituted alkynes were also effective and provided high to excellent yields, regardless of the kind of the tethering chain (**2t–x**). The presence of other primary or secondary alkyl chains was also possible to give diboronates **2y–ab**. TMS derivative **1ac** gave rise to the corresponding-1-silylalkenylboronates **2ac** in high yield. The process also tolerates substitution on the propargyl and allyl carbon atoms, affording the expected products in excellent to quantitative yields (**2af–ah**). However, no stereocontrol on the formation of the new stereogenic center was observed. The poorest results were obtained for the reactions of enynes **1ad**, containing a terminal alkyne; and for 1,7-enyne **1ae**, which afforded the six-membered ring product in just 18%.

Chart 1. Ni-catalyzed diborylative cyclization of enynes.^a

[a] Conditions: enyne **1** (0.2 mmol), B₂pin₂ (0.21 mmol), Ni(cod)₂ (5 mol%), **L1** (5 mol%) and *i*-Pr₂O (1 mL) at 60 °C for 5 h. Isolated yields by column chromatography. [b] Toluene was used instead of *i*-Pr₂O. [c] A mixture of two diastereoisomers was obtained d.r. = 1:1.7 (**2af**), d.r. = 1:3.7 (**2ag**), d.r. = 1:1.2 (**2ah**).

With the aim of illustrating the synthetic utility of the obtained diboronates, we performed some functionalization reactions. Thus, oxidation of both boronate groups gave the corresponding hydroxy-ketone **3** in high yield.

Scheme 2. Functionalization of diboronates.

More interestingly, we succeeded at performing an orthogonal derivatization of diboronates **2u** and **2k** by selective Suzuki cross-coupling reactions. Firstly, we coupled the alkenylboronate moiety with iodobenzene to obtain **4**. Then, the remaining alkyboronate group was converted into the trifluoroborate salts **5**, which were used in subsequent Suzuki cross-couplings to give compounds **6** (Scheme 2). There is no need to have different boronates, such as Bpin and Bdan^{5g,7b}

In order to get insight into the reaction mechanism, we have performed some experiments. Thus, when simple alkenes or alkynes were subjected to the optimized conditions, we did not observe borylation of none of the substrates. On the other hand, the stoichiometric reaction of enynes **1f** or **1k** with Ni(cod)₂ and **L1** in the absence of boron reagent, followed by hydrolysis with DCl in D₂O led to the corresponding deuterated cyclic derivatives **1f'** and **1k'**. These results suggest the formation of an intermediate complex containing both alkyl- and alkenyl-Ni bonds. In fact, we could obtain dark red single crystals resulting from the stoichiometric reaction of **1a** and Ni(cod)₂-tpy.

Scheme 3. Essays to probe the reaction pathway.

X-Ray diffraction analysis revealed the structure of a fascinating bimetallic complex containing a carbocycle and two Ni(I)-tpy units bound to alkyl and alkenyl carbon ligands (**7**, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Two different views of the crystal structure of dinuclear Ni complex **7** derived from **1a**.

The short Ni-Ni distance (2.97 Å) indicates a strong interaction between both metals (van der Waals radius for Ni is 1.63 Å). This is reminiscent of the structure of MeNi(tpy), in which a weaker intermolecular interaction between Ni atom was observed in the solid state (3.18 Å).¹⁸ Both metal atoms are formally Ni(I), and therefore the structure of the complex corresponds to an oxidative cyclometalation with each metal increasing its oxidation state by one unit. We envisioned two possible mechanisms for the formation of **7**, and calculations at DFT level have been performed on **1a** as a model to probe their feasibility (Scheme 4, see Supporting Information for details).

Scheme 4. Top: Calculated possible reaction pathways for the formation of **7**. Bottom: Reaction energies for the reaction of **7** with diboron reagent. ΔG (kcal mol⁻¹) are calculated with M06-2x functional, using 6-31G(d) (C,H,N,O), LANL2DZ (Ni) basis set, in diisopropylether (PCM) (activation energies in italics).

Thus, the process could involve the cyclization of a bimetallic precursor containing two Ni(tpy) units coordinated to each unsaturation (**III**). Formation of **III** is exoergic and its evolution to **7** would take place with a moderate activation energy (28.2 kcal mol⁻¹) compatible with a process taking place at 60 °C. Alternatively, oxidative cyclometalation could occur from a mononuclear Ni species with both the alkyne and the alkene coordinated to the metal (**I**). Activation energy for the formation of metalacy-

cle **II** from this complex is lower (17.3 kcal mol⁻¹), albeit the corresponding transition state lies above the above mentioned one. On the other hand, a triplet transition state, **TS(I-II)t**, lying 1.1 kcal mol⁻¹ below **TS(III-7)** would lead to the formation of **II**. Subsequent comproportionation with N(tpy) would afford species **7** as well. Complex **7** shows a triplet ground state according to its EPR spectrum ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.1$, see Supporting Information). Calculated triplet state for **7** is only 3.1 kcal mol⁻¹ more stable compared to the singlet. When we subjected complex **7** to reaction with an excess of B₂pin₂, simulating the reaction relative concentrations, bis(boronate) **2a** was formed, but in moderate yield (41% NMR yield, Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Formation of complex **7** with stoichiometric amount of catalyst and subsequent reaction with B₂pin₂.

Computational and experimental results are not conclusive to decide whether the reaction takes place through monometallic intermediate **II** or by direct formation of **7**, since DFT methods overestimate the stability of high-spin states, and therefore, the computed energy for **TS(I-II)t** is not fully reliable. In addition, the low energy of dinuclear complex **7** suggests that it could be a resting state rather than a reaction intermediate. Moreover, inspection of the structure of **7** makes difficult to guess how this complex could react with B₂pin₂. We have studied the interaction of **II** with the boron reagent (Scheme 4, bottom). Exploration of the potential energy surface strongly suggests that oxidative addition of the B-B bond to give a Ni(IV) intermediate does not take place. Instead, we propose a σ -bond metathesis, which may involve both Ni-C bonds to give either intermediate **IV** or **V**. Reaction involving cleavage of the alkenyl-Ni bond to provide **IV** seems more feasible, since it is exoergic (-3.4 kcal mol⁻¹), whereas formation of **V** is endoergic(+3.5 kcal mol⁻¹). Finally, downhill C-B reductive elimination would give the final diboronate and would regenerate the Ni(0) catalyst.

In conclusion, synthetically useful carbo- and heterocycles containing and alkyl- and alkenylboronate units can be efficiently synthesized from enynes with inexpensive catalyst. Activation of the organic substrate takes place prior to reaction with the borylation reagent. Further studies to ascertain the reaction mechanism, especially regarding the activation of diboron derivatives with novel dinuclear Ni(I)-Ni(I) complexes are underway.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Experimental procedures and analytical data for all compounds, X-ray diffraction details, as well as computational methods, energies and coordinates. The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications

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SYNOPSIS TOC . Full atom-economical Ni-catalyzed diborylative cyclization of enynes affords synthetically useful diboronates. A dinuclear bis(organometallic) Ni(I) complex has been isolated.

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